

SYNTAXEME ANALYSIS OF SUBORDINATE COMPONENTS IN SIMPLE SENTENCE

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Annotation: In this article, we find that the change of differential syntactic-semantic signs is a result of the interaction of syntactic units through the syntaxeme analysis of the subordinate components of a simple sentence, one syntactic unit means more than one function. We also consider the syntaxeme of the syntactic units in the deep structure of a sentence by analyzing the syntactic units that come from the surface structure of the sentence, their interrelationships, and differential syntactic features by modeling methods.

Keywords: deep structure of the simple sentence, syntaxeme analysis, differential syntactic, differential syntactic-semantic features, transformational method, the surface structure of the sentence, syntactic units, unclear subordinate component, componential model, junctional model;

Аннотация: В данной статье мы обнаруживаем, что смена дифференциальных синтаксико-семантических признаков происходит в результате взаимодействия синтаксических единиц посредством синтаксемного анализа придаточных компонентов простого предложения, одна синтаксическая единица означает более одной функции. Мы также рассматриваем синтаксемные синтаксических единиц в глубинной структуре предложения путем анализа синтаксических единиц, исходящих из поверхностной структуры предложения, их взаимосвязей и дифференциальных синтаксических признаков методами моделирования.

Ключевые слова: глубинная структура простого предложения, синтаксемный анализ, дифференциальный синтаксис, дифференциальные синтаксико-семантические признаки, трансформационный прием, поверхностная структура предложения, синтаксические единицы, неясный подчинительный компонент, компонентная модель, соединительная модель;

Anatatsiya: Mazkur maqolada biz sodda gap tarkibidagi tobe komponentlarning sintaksem tahlili orqali sintaktik birliklarning o`zaro aloqasi natijasida differensial sintaktik-semantik belgilarning o`zgarib borishi, bir sintaktik birlik birdan ortiq vazifani anglatishini aniqlaymiz. Shuningdek, gapning tashqi tarkibida kelgan sintaktik birliklarni, ularning o`zaro sintaktik aloqalarini hamda differensial sintaktik belgilarini modellashtirish usullari orqali tahlil qilib

gapning ichki qurilmasidagi sintaktik birliklarning sintaktik sathda semantikasini ko`rib chiqamiz.

Kalit so`zlar: gapning ichki qurilmasi, sintaksemlar, differensial sintaktik, differensial sintaktik-semantik xususiyatlar, transformatsiya metodi, gapning tashqi qurilmasi, sintaktik birliklar, noyadroviy tobe component, komponent model, yunksion model.

It is known from the history of linguistics that English and American linguists have different approaches to the syntactic analysis of sentence. Representatives of American structuralism studied grammar on a formalistic basis. Their experiments made it necessary to focus on semantics at the syntactic level. Using chain analysis, Z.S. Harris advances the idea of dividing the sentence structure into elementary parts of speech and adjuncts based on the distributive method. L.E. Longaker also follows him and uses the method of chain analysis, dividing the sentence directly into participants. The syntactic analysis of a sentence is limited to the analysis of the participants directly, using a chain method. Therefore, this method of analysis is limited to the morphological features of the units involved in the sentence and cannot proceed to the synthesis process. Eventually, with the advent of transformed grammar, a method of analyzing the syntactic units of a sentence by segmenting and using distributive methods emerged and evolved. Over time, these methods of linguistic analysis have evolved and taken on a new look.

Although A.S. Smirnitsky and other aforementioned scholars have made significant contributions to the study of grammatical features on the basis of distributive, transformational, tagmematic, and chain analysis methods there exist some problematic aspects. In this regard, our institute PhD. R. M. Asadov fully explained in his dissertation, that is, to determine the valence of syntactic units in the speech device on the basis of syntactic relations, to determine their differential syntactic, differential syntactic-semantic features and the possibility of combining with other syntaxemes on the basis of certain syntactic relations. In componential analysis, syntactic elements form the surface device of sentences. In syntaxeme analysis, however, syntactic units include the deep structure of sentences.

The linguistic methods created by A. M. Mukhin well as a number of other scientific researches were used effectively in the study of this issue. Based on this method of linguistic analysis, the subordinate syntactic units in the English simple sentence are determined on the basis of syntactic relations. The success of this approach to sentence analysis has been recognized in some scientific

studies. In the analysis of sentences involving subordinate syntactic units into syntaxemes, mainly from the categorical differential syntactic-semantic signs **substantiality** (syntactic unit representing a person or object), **proessuality** (syntactic unit representing this action or situation) and **qualificativity** (quality, volume, quantity, the syntactic unit representing the case;) will be the focus of most syntaxeme analysis. The syntactic units that express the unnuclear subordinate component are linked to the base or dominant component in the sentence by subordinative connection. These dependent components can occur in different syntactic places in a sentence and represent differential syntactic-semantic characters. Syntactically analyzing the following examples, we identify the syntactic-semantic characters they represent:

1. They will tax it).
2. I went to school .
3. I am going away at midnight

In the first sentence, the subordinate component represents the substantial object syntaxeme. In order to prove it, it is enough to turn this sentence into a transformation passivation:

They will tax it→It will be taxed by them.

In the second sentence, to determine whether a monovalent subordinate component to school means substantiality from categorical signs, from non-categorical signs to locative allative (place: the direction of a person or action in space, use of preposition `to` syntaxeme, the to school subordinate syntactic unit must be replaced by adverbial elements here / there:

I went to school→ I went there.

In the next sentence, the monovalent dependent component at midnight represents the substantial temporal (time) (SbTm) syntaxeme. To prove this syntaxeme, the at midnight component can be replaced by the tense forms then, now, etc.

I am going away at midnight → I am going away now / then.

This model reflects three features of each syntactic unit in a sentence: syntactic function, morphological expression, and categorical and non-categorical semantic features. The componential structure, morphological features and differential syntactic-semantic features of the analyzed sentences can be modeled as follows:

Analysis of the examples shows that non-nuclear subordinate components are subject to the nuclear predicative 2 components of sentence, which represent object, locative allative, temporal, social syntax on the basis of substantiality.

The syntactic unit that is subordinate to the syntactic unit that replaces the 2 components of the nuclear predicate is the substantive agent syntax me.

The scientific significance of this approach to sentence analysis is to clarify the features of the theory of syntactic semantic analysis at the language level, to show the importance of the role of syntactic relationships in determining the semantics of language units at the syntactic level. The semantics of the syntactic units involved in the sentence structure is illustrated in terms of functional syntax through the use of models. This approach to simple sentence analysis in English serves to solve some of the most controversial problems in theoretical grammar.

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